

Implementation of Prohibition of Employment as Manual Scavengers and their Rehabilitation Act, 2013 in India- A Comparative Literature Review

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Abstract

The Prohibition of Employment as Manual Scavengers and their Rehabilitation Act, 2013 was apparently upgraded to include all whoever worked without proper physical safety protection and direct human contact to manually clean human faecal waste to Prohibition of Manual scavenging practices. Manual scavenging is the removal of excreta (Night Soil) manually from "Dry Toilets" the toilets without modern flush system. Manual Scavenging is a cast based and hereditary occupation for Dalits, manual scavenging in India is mostly done by the people considered as lower castes or untouchables. . This Paper specifically deals with various available literature and aims.

This paper specifically deals with the Implementation of Prohibition of Employment as Manual Scavengers and their Rehabilitation Act, 2013 that addresses the problems of manual scavengers in India as a mean of occupation and to explore the causes and reasons for the continuance of such practices in India.

Keywords: 1.Manual Scavengers, 2. faecal waste, 3. Dalits, 4. Prohibition of Employment as Manual Scavengers and their Rehabilitation Act, 2013.

Objectives of Paper

1. The purpose of this study is to study the impact of The Prohibition of Employment as Manual Scavengers and their Rehabilitation Act, 2013.
2. The present paper also focuses on recent deaths in due to engagement in manual scavenging in Various Parts of India.

Introduction:

Manual Scavenging is a cast based and hereditary occupation for Dalits (Baruah A.2014). Manual scavenging in India is mostly done by people considered as lower castes or untouchables. Social exclusion is the main cause why some community is pushed into manual scavenging. Regardless of a number of retrograding welfare actions as well as legal provisions nothing important has happened (Shiv Prakash katiyar 2017).

Manual Scavenging is the removal of excreta (night soil) manually from dry toilets without modern flush system. The system of building public toilets and employing people to remove excreta was introduced during British rules in India, when big cities were formed like municipalities were formed that time often containers were used in such toilets that needed to be emptied daily.

The socio cultural and economical realities of modern India reveal a series of paradoxes. While legally manual scavenging is banned, caste based occupation and inherited poverty that followed by generations are the main reason behind the practice. The manual scavengers have different names in different parts of countries like Bhangi's in Gujarat and Uttarpradesh, Phakis in Andhra Pradesh, sikkaliars in Tamil Nadu. Refusal to perform such manual task leads to physical abuse and a social boycott.

A random survey conducted by the action in 2002 in six states- Madhya Pradesh, Andhra Pradesh, Orrissa, Uttar Pradesh, Rajasthan and Bihar claimed that manual scavengers were found working on at least 30,000 dry toilets. The survey also emphasis on that, these scavengers faces severe discrimination even from other group of society (Action Aid, 2003).

Unlike other studies, we undertook this review to understand how law framework protects the rights of people and prohibition of manual scavengers in caste dominant society.

The Employment of Manual Scavengers and Construction of Dry Latrines (Prohibition) Act, 1993 defines 'manual scavenger' as "a person engaged in or employed for manually carrying human excreta". The employment of manual scavengers is prohibited as a criminal offence.

The recently enacted Prohibition of Employment as Manual Scavengers and their Rehabilitation Act, 2013 gives a detailed definition of 'manual scavenger' as:

"a person engaged or employed, at the commencement of this Act or at any time thereafter, by an individual or local authority or an agency or a contractor, for manually cleaning, carrying, disposing of, or otherwise handling in any manner, human excreta in an insanitary latrine or in an open drain or pit into which the human excreta from the insanitary latrines is disposed of, or on a railway track or in such other spaces or premises, as the Central Government or a State Government may notify, before the excreta fully decomposes in such manner as may be prescribed..."(PEMSR-2013)

In practice, these definitions are incomplete. It is important, therefore, to turn to other social and historical materials to understand what manual scavenging really means. The Asian Human Rights Commission, for instance, describes manual scavenging in the following terms:

"Manual scavenging in India is officially defined as 'lifting and removal of human excreta manually', at private homes and toilets maintained by municipal authorities. The practice consists of gathering human excreta from individual or community dry latrines with bare hands, brooms or metal scrapers into woven baskets or buckets. This the scavengers then carry on their heads, shoulders or against their hips, (and in wheelbarrows if they can afford it) into dumping sites or water bodies. Apart from this, many scavengers are similarly employed to collect, carry and dispose excreta from sewers, septic tanks, drains and railway tracks." (Asia Human Rights Commission, 2009).

Key Recommendations to Indian Central and State Authorities

- Identify all individuals currently engaged in manual scavenging and those who have engaged in the practice since it was outlawed under the 1993 Act (so the latter are entitled to benefits under the 2013 Act).
- Ensure that rehabilitation entitlements under the 2013 Act—including financial assistance, scholarships, housing, alternative livelihood support, and other important legal and programmatic assistance—are available to manual scavenging communities.
- Take immediate steps to ensure that officials effectively intervene to stop communities from being coerced to practice manual scavenging, including when members of such communities face threats and intimidation for attempting to leave manual scavenging. The steps should include holding officials accountable for properly enforcing relevant laws, including the 2013 Act and the Scheduled Castes and Scheduled Tribes (Prevention of Atrocities) Act, 1989.
- Strictly enforce the law against local government officials who themselves employ people to work as manual scavengers.
- Enact the Scheduled Castes and Scheduled Tribes (Prevention of Atrocities) Amendment Ordinance, 2014, No. 1 of 2014 (Human Rights Watch, 2014)

Efforts in India to End Manual Scavenging

- 1955 Protection of Civil Rights Act, 1955, enacted to abolish untouchability, and social disabilities arising out of untouchability, against Scheduled Castes.
- 1977 Protection of Civil Rights Act, 1955, revised, making untouchability practices cognizable and non compoundable offenses, and increasing punishment.

- 1981 Integrated Low Cost Sanitation Scheme authorizes funds to poor urban households to convert dry latrines to water flush latrines.
- 1989 Sub-Committee of the Task force Constituted by the Planning Commission estimates there are 72,050 million dry latrines in India. National Scheduled Castes and Scheduled Tribes Finance and Development Corporation established to provide financial assistance to all scheduled castes and scheduled tribes, including safai karmacharis. Low Cost Sanitation for Liberation of Manual Scavengers scheme formulated to convert dry latrines and construct new sanitary latrines. Parliament passes the Scheduled Castes and Scheduled Tribes (Prevention of Atrocities) Act.
- 1992 National Scheme of Liberation of Scavengers and their Dependents launched. Constitution (Seventy fourth) Amendment Act makes sanitation the responsibility of Urban Local Bodies.
- 1993 Parliament enacts The Employment of Manual Scavengers and Construction of Dry Latrines (Prohibition) Act. Parliament passes the National Commission for Safai Karamcharis Act.
- 1994 National Commission for Safai Karamcharis constituted under the National Commission for Safai Karamcharis Act, 1993, to monitor and recommend specific programs.
- 1996 National Human Rights Commission sends letters to various authorities on elimination of manual scavenging.
- 1997 National Safai Karmacharis Finance and Development Corporation incorporated by central government as an apex institution for the socioeconomic uplift of safai karmacharis and their dependents and to extend concessions and financial assistance to beneficiaries for income generation. National Human Rights Commission writes to chief ministers to emphasize the need to adopt and enforce the Employment of Manual Scavengers and Construction of Dry Latrines (Prohibition) Act, 1993.
- 1999 National Human Rights Commission sets up a group comprised of representatives from concerned ministries and the Planning Commission to make recommendations to end manual scavenging.
- 2000 National Commission for Safai Karamcharis submits its first report to parliament noting that the 1993 Act is not being implemented effectively, estimates that the number of manual scavengers is 577,288, and reports that people are employed to do manual scavenging by the military engineering works, the army, public sector, and Indian Railways. 2001 UN World Conference against Racism held in Durban, South Africa. Caste is described as descent based discrimination.
- 2002 Ministry of Social Justice and Empowerment estimates there are 78,700 million people engaged in manual scavenging. At 27th session of the UN Commission on Human Rights, Working Group on Contemporary Forms of Slavery presents note to the Sub-Commission on the Promotion and Protection of Human Rights and calls upon India to press all states to implement the Employment of Manual Scavengers and Construction of Dry Latrines (Prohibition) Act, 1993, and to prosecute all officials responsible for perpetuation of the practice. On Independence Day, August 15, Prime Minister Atal Bihari Vajpayee announces 15-point program to speed up the liberation and rehabilitation of manual scavengers.
- 2003 Writ Petition filed by Safai Karmacharis Andolan and six other civil society organizations requests that the Supreme Court take effective steps to eliminate manual scavenging and the use of dry latrines. Report submitted by the Comptroller and Auditor General, evaluating the National Scheme for Liberation and Rehabilitation of Scavengers, concludes that scheme “has failed to achieve its objectives even after 10 years of implementation.” Ministry of Social Justice and Empowerment estimates there are 67.6 million people engaged as manual scavengers. 2004 The Planning Commission develops a national action plan for total eradication of manual scavenging by 2007.
- 2005 National Commission for Safai Karamcharis estimates that there are about 67.6 million manual scavengers, 5.4 million dry latrines in urban areas, and 2.4 million dry latrines in rural areas.
- 2006 National Human Rights Commission tells representatives of state governments to end manual scavenging within six months.

- 2007 Self-Employment Scheme for Rehabilitation of Manual Scavengers initiated to provide training, loans, and subsidies for alternate occupations. International Labor Organization's 96th Session releases "Equality at Work" report, which mentions manual scavenging. National Human Rights Commission calls on all states that have not yet adopted Employment of Manual Scavengers and Construction of Dry Latrines (Prohibition) Act, 1993, to do so at the earliest time possible, calls for coordination between various governmental and nongovernmental agencies and an exchange of good practices between states, and makes specific recommendations to state and central governments on identification, liberation, and rehabilitation of manual scavengers. According to survey reports received from the states, the Self Employment Scheme for Rehabilitation of Manual Scavengers estimates that the total number of manual scavengers and their dependents is 770,338. From this number 427,870 people received assistance under the National Scheme for Liberation and Rehabilitation of Manual Scavengers, 2002, and 342,468 were yet to be rehabilitated.
- 2008 Integrated Low Cost Sanitation Scheme reviewed and new guidelines put in place following implementation difficulties.
- 2010 Ministry of Social Justice and Empowerment reports that by the end of 2009, a total of 69,137 manual scavengers were provided loans to for alternate occupations under the Self Employment Scheme for Rehabilitation of Manual Scavengers, 13,700 intended beneficiaries were yet to be covered, and efforts being made to cover remaining beneficiaries by 2010. All concerned state governments confirm that all eligible and willing manual scavengers have been rehabilitated in alternative occupations under the Scheme for Rehabilitation of Manual Scavengers. National Advisory Council resolution expresses "deep anguish at the official failure to eradicate manual scavenging, the most degrading surviving practice of untouchability in the country." Based on surveys, Garima Abhiyan and Mahila Mukti Gathbandhan estimate that the number of people engaged in manual scavenging across the country is 350,000. This does not include safai karmacharis employed by the Indian Railways, panchayats, and municipal corporations and made to manually clean excrement.
- 2011 National Human Rights Commission releases report, "Know Your Rights: Human Rights and Manual Scavenging." Consultation Meeting on Eradication of Manual Scavenging and Rehabilitation of Manual Scavengers is organized by the Ministry of Social Justice and Empowerment. The ministry establishes task force for a new national level survey to identify manual scavengers. Prime Minister Manmohan Singh reiterates government's determination to completely eradicate manual scavenging in a very short time.
- 2012 House Listing and Housing Census 2011 released by Registrar General shows there are still 2.6 million insanitary latrines in the country that are cleaned manually. The Registrar General determines there are three kinds of insanitary latrines—those cleaned by people, those connected to open drains, and dry latrines. Accordingly, the Ministry of Social Justice recommends stronger central legislation rather than amendment to the 1993 Act since the 1993 Act only covers dry latrines. Prohibition of Employment as Manual Scavengers and their Rehabilitation Bill, 2012, introduced in Lok Sabha and referred to a parliamentary committee for review. UN human right rapporteurs on water and sanitation, Catarina de Albuquerque, and the rapporteur on contemporary forms of slavery, Gulnara Shahinan, call upon states to address caste-based discrimination. European Parliament passes a resolution criticizing caste-based discrimination in India.
- 2013 UN High Commissioner for Human Rights Navi Pillay appeals to the Indian government to pass new legislation to end manual scavenging. Parliament passes the Prohibition of Employment as Manual Scavengers Act, 2013.
- 2014 Supreme Court decision in *Safai Karmachari Andolan v. Union of India* directs that all people working as manual scavengers be rehabilitated "based on the principles of justice and transformation" and reiterates that states have a duty to implement the 2013 Act. Shortly before taking office as prime minister, Narendra Modi says: "My identity is of a Hindutvawadi [one who promotes the Hindu religion], but I say build toilets before you build temples." (Human Right Watch, 2014)

Methodology

In this paper we aim to analyze whether existing law protect the rights of people and available literature for describing actual image of manual scavengers in India.

The available literature will help the researchers to analyze and compare the existing structure and situation of people engaged in manual scavenging.

The analysis of all the reviewed reports is as mentioned below.

Sr. No.	Government Reports/Journals/Press Releases.	Outcomes
1	Government reports, Policy statements and Committee reports:	
1.1	6th meeting of central monitoring committee to review implementation of "Prohibition of Employment as Manual Scavengers and their Rehabilitation Act, 2013 held	Recommendation by government of India addressing current situations of manual scavenging in India and focuses on upliftment policies to frame for their rehabilitation.
1.2	National Human Right Commission Recommendations on Manual Scavenging and Sanitation.	Recommendation by National Commission on Human Rights regarding prohibition of cleaning dry toilets and adopting new technologies for addressing these issues.
2	Peer reviewed literature journals & books:	
2.1	Manual Scavenging Act and Municipal Waste Water Workers in India – Policy and Practice	Reports focus on existing coverage of manual scavengers in all over the India and related hazards. Reports address the humiliation and discriminatory approaches.
2.2	Discrimination and Violence against Dalit women engaged in Manual Scavenging: Legal Remedies and Beyond.	Violence against the specific communities and social exclusion of families engaged in manual scavenging and movement for rights of Safai Karmachari.
2.3	Moving Forward: Ending Manual Scavenging in Paliyad.	Adopting new technological advanced techniques for cleaning septic tanks and stigma related to this profession.
2.4	The Prohibition of Employment as Manual Scavengers and their Rehabilitation Act, 2013: Scope & Challenges.	Supreme courts comments on taking proper steps for eradication of manual scavenging and taking protective initiatives for safety.
3	Press Releases:-	
3.1	39 Deaths In 100 Days: How Manual Scavenging Continues to Exist in India despite It Being Illegal.	As per 2011 census, 1, 82,505 rural households depend on income based on manual scavenging and contrast in data produced by various states. 39 Deaths in only 2017
3.2	88 Manual Scavenging Deaths in 3 Years.	144 cases in Tamilnadu and 131 cases in Gujarat and judgment by supreme court to pay compensation to all who died in sewage since 1993 and provide 10 lakh to their families.
3.3	50 People Died Cleaning Sewers in the First Six Months of 2019.	As per data receive from Safai Karmchari also 50 People died in first six months of 2019.

Analysis:

The study is purely based on secondary data wherein researchers have tried to describe the concern in systematic & appropriate manner for the same various reports on related topics have been studied.

1. Government reports, Policy statements and Committee reports:

1.1 6th meeting of central monitoring committee to review implementation of "Prohibition of Employment as Manual Scavengers and their Rehabilitation Act, 2013 held

Addressing on the occasion, Shri Thaawarchand Gehlot said that the Government is keen to eradicate the manual scavenging on a time bound basis for which the State Governments have been urged to implement the provisions of the MS Act, 2013 in letter and spirit. This important Central Act was enacted by the Parliament in September, 2013 and has come into force in December, 2014. It aims at complete elimination of the manual scavenging in its various manifestations and comprehensive rehabilitation of the identified manual scavengers.

He said that 13,657 manual scavengers have, so far, been identified in 13 States. However, keeping in view the large number of insanitary latrines replaced in house listing and household data of Census-2011, the States have been asked to revisit their survey by using the wider definition of manual scavenging as given in the MS Act, 2013 to ensure that all the persons who are cleaning un-decomposed septage manually are identified and listed as manual scavengers.

The Minister said that Government is implementing a Self- Employment Scheme for the Rehabilitation of identified manual scavengers under which onetime cash assistance; skill development training and loan subsidy are provided for rehabilitation of identified manual scavengers onetime cash assistance of Rs.40000/- each has been released to 12991 identified manual scavengers till date. Proposals for skill development training for 13587 manual scavengers and their dependents and self-employment proposals for 944 manual scavengers and their dependents have been sanctioned (Ministry of Social Justice and Empowerment, Government of India 2018).

1.2 National Human Right Commission Recommendations on Manual Scavenging and Sanitation

National Human Rights Commission has made recommendations for the public authorities while dealing with issues on Manual Scavenging and Sanitation. These are as follows:-

1. Though surveys on manual scavenging have been conducted, several anomalies have been found. Therefore, periodic comprehensive survey, at least once in three years, should be conducted in collaboration with credible NGOs. It should cover dry latrines, manual scavengers and alternative livelihood options for rehabilitation.
2. As per the information available with the Ministry of Housing and Urban Poverty Alleviation, Government of India, there are dry latrines in UP, Bihar, J&K and Assam. Therefore, these four States should take all necessary measures for the complete conversion and demolition of dry latrines and rehabilitation of manual scavengers in their respective states. Based on comprehensive Survey, all other States should also take necessary steps.
3. Jammu & Kashmir and Delhi must quicken the pace of adoption of the Act which should be done at the earliest.
4. The Definition of manual scavengers is different from sanitary workers and all authorities may restrict to the definition of manual scavenging as given in the Employment of Manual Scavengers and Construction of Dry Latrines (Prohibition) Act, 1993.
5. The presence of too many agencies is often delaying the elimination of the practice of manual scavenging and the rehabilitation work. Therefore, District Magistrates should be made the nodal agency and joint instructions from the three Central Ministries concerned with manual scavenging should be issued to the States/ Union Territories and the District Magistrates to take necessary steps for coordination and convergence of efforts. At State level also, there should be a coordinating body to monitor framing of appropriate rules and regulations, survey as envisaged in recommendation 1, conversion or demolition of dry latrines, rehabilitation of manual scavengers, prosecution of defaulters etc. The issue of lack of space and scarcity of water in some pockets in some States has to be addressed by adopting appropriate technology and methodologies.

6. The municipal and panchayat bye laws of the States should have provisions not to allow the construction of any new house with dry latrine or without a water shield latrine or sanitary latrines with appropriate technology and measures should be taken so that dry latrines made in the past can be demolished and new water shield latrines or sanitary latrines with appropriate technology be constructed. There should be a time bound limit for conversion of dry latrines into wet latrines and construction of new latrines. It should be one of the criteria for deciding grants to Municipal bodies and there should be some measures to take penal action against municipalities not fulfilling their obligations in this regard.
7. The Ministry of Social Justice and Empowerment may evolve modalities for payment of immediate relief of Rs.10, 000 to manual scavengers as in the case of bonded labour, pending their rehabilitation.
8. The scholarship to the children of manual scavengers should not be stopped even after their parents have been liberated from manual scavenging and rehabilitated.
9. It should be ensured that the identified manual scavenger families who are entitled to get the BPL cards are issued the BPL cards Banks must simplify their procedure for giving loans to manual scavengers for their rehabilitation.
10. State Governments must issue advertisements in leading newspapers about cases of manual scavengers and dry latrines and also publish the same on the notice boards of the Panchayat/ Municipal bodies. The list of identified manual scavengers should be displayed on website and at important public places for inspection by public at large and must be given wide publicity. Any person who is left out can approach the notified authority. After identification, the District Magistrate should issue a certificate to the manual scavenger based on which all concerned agencies should extend benefits to which he or she may be eligible. The State Human Rights Commissions should start monitoring elimination of manual scavenging and consequent rehabilitation of manual scavengers in the States. (National Human Right Commission, 2018).

2. Peer reviewed literature journals & books:

Despite Government rehabilitation schemes, millions of Dalits, most of them are women are forced to continue the intolerable manual scavenging. This practice has been observed from Kashmir to Kanyakumari. Those involved in manual scavenging due to the prevailing of dry latrines not only suffer from the inhuman pain of scavenging human faeces but also go through the agonizing pain and humiliation of discrimination, occupational health hazards of peril, untouchability and social exclusion. (Minakshisundaram N. 2012)

Under the caste system there are mainly four castes while castes are divided in sub- castes. Dalit caste also has many sub-castes such as Sweeper, Basor, 'Bhangi', Balmiki and traditionally they engaged in manual scavenging in India. They are the person in the government offices called sweeper or Safai Karamchari (SK). Safai Karmchari Andolan (SKA) - is a National Social movement in India; struggling to eradicate the practice of manual scavenging and fighting for equality, dignity of the manual scavenging communities (Pachouri, S. 2008).

Due to the ubiquitous practice of open defecation, exposed wastewater running through the village streets, and lack of understanding about germ theory and hygiene, people are exposed to the risk of health consequences. Manual scavengers, however, face a dual risk of exposure to harmful pathogens in both their environment and. Scavengers are consistently exposed to human and animal waste with minimal or no protective equipment. Anecdotal evidence that there were no safe equipment(s) available and even if it were available many scavengers prefer not using the protective gear, due to issues of comfort and stigma (Sudhalkar, A.2011).

The Supreme Court pulled up the Centre for its failure to enact a law to ban manual scavenging despite giving assurances many times earlier that it would soon amend the relevant Act (The Times of India, 2013). Sankaran (2008) argued that the National Commission for Safai Karamcharis Act, 1993 has conferred no powers at all to the Commission except that of calling for information, thus reducing the Commission to an advisory bereft of any real authority. On 18th September 2013, the Prohibition of Employment as Manual Scavengers and their Rehabilitation Act, 2013 was passed on. It has been critiqued that this law doesn't eliminate the manual scavenging practices. The explanation in the Act under section 2 (1) (b) has legitimized manual scavenging by stating that it can be done by using protective gears and other devices. Manual scavenging must be prohibited in any form. (Action Aid, 2013).

3. Press Releases:

3.1 39 Deaths in 100 Days: How Manual Scavenging Continues To Exist In India Despite It Being Illegal

The death of four men while cleaning a tank raised justified questions on the continuing practice of manual scavenging that exists till date. A derogatory practice, manual scavenging is confined to people belonging to lower castes and as a profession is inhuman with low pay and nearly nil safety measures provided. Manual scavenging remains a dominant practice across India, despite the passage of The Employment of Manual Scavenging and Construction of Dry Latrines (Prohibition) Act in 1993. The Act was again revised 20 years.

later in 2013, and stressed on not only eradicating manual scavenging but rehabilitating families which were dependent on manual scavenging as a profession. With 39 deaths in the last 100 days in 2017 alone, it is a right time to ask how effective have been the measures taken to eradicate the practice of manual scavenging?

While the Prime Minister Narendra Modi has declared the eradication of manual scavenging by 2019, the ground reality is starkly contrasting and fulfillment of the Prime Minister's promise looks difficult. As per the 2011 Socio-Economic and Case Census, 1, 82,505 rural households in India were dependent on manual scavenging for income. The biggest problem in addressing the issue of manual scavengers is the lack of Central and state governments to accept that the practice still exists and declare actual figures related to the number of manual scavengers.

In July 2016, a meeting was convened by the National Commission for Scheduled Castes (NCSC), where representatives of states and union territories were asked to share data related to the number of dry latrines and manual scavengers. The data submitted however, showed severe mismatch. As of December 2015, Telangana reported 1, 57,321 dry latrines but zero manual scavengers, a barely believable figure. Himachal Pradesh declared 854 dry latrines in the state but zero manual scavengers, while Chandigarh reported 4,391 dry latrines but only 3 manual scavengers. The numbers clearly show the reluctance of state governments to identify the existence of manual scavenging as a prevalent practice. Rajasthan, Punjab and West Bengal were the only states which reported an increase in the number of manual scavengers in the last two years (Dutta S. (2017).

3.2 88 manual scavenging deaths in 3 years

The number of deaths of sanitation workers while cleaning septic tanks and sewers has risen, despite a ban on manual scavenging, with 620 cases reported since 1993, of which 88 occurred in the past three years, according to the Social Justice and Empowerment Ministry. To a question by MPs Asaduddin Owaisi and Syed Imtiaz Jaleel on Tuesday, Social Justice and Empowerment Minister of State Ramdas Athawale told the Lok Sabha that compensation had been given in 445 cases, partial settlement in 58 cases, while 117 cases were pending.

In 445 cases the full amount had been paid, while partial compensation had been given in 58 cases, the reply said. Of the 15 States and Union Territories that submitted details to the Ministry, Tamil Nadu had the highest number of sewer deaths with 144 cases, followed by Gujarat with 131. Of the 88 cases reported in 2017, 2018 and 2019, till June 14, compensation was pending in 52 cases.

The MPs had questioned the government over whether it planned on amending the Prohibition of Employment as Manual Scavengers and their Rehabilitation Act, 2013 in order to make it mandatory for States to report such cases. In response, the Minister said the Act had laid down a mechanism of monitoring its implementation through vigilance committees and monitoring committees at different levels, so there was "no proposal" to amend it as of now.

On the data of 15 States and Union Territories, a senior official said "some States had not reported and some had reported nil", leading to the possibility of the actual deaths from manual scavenging being higher. A Supreme Court order from March 27, 2014 makes it mandatory for the government to identify all those who died in sewerage work since 1993 and provide ₹ 10 lakh each as compensation to their families.

In another reply to a question by MP Vishnu Dayal Ram, the minister told the Lok Sabha that 53,598 manual scavengers had been identified from December 6, 2013 till June 30, 2019. While the Act says no one can employ a person for manual scavenging and lays down punishments for those who do, the minister said "there have been no reports from any state/Union Territory regarding conviction in such cases".(Nath D.2019).

3.3 50 People Died Cleaning Sewers in the First Six Months of 2019

Data collated by the National Commission for Safai Karamcharis (NCSK) reveals that at least 50 persons have died cleaning sewers in the first six months of 2019 alone. According to a report in the *Indian Express*, the figure in question, by the NCSK's own admission, is an underestimation as it only accounts for the number of deaths caused by cleaning sewers in only eight states of Uttar Pradesh, Haryana, Delhi, Punjab, Gujarat, Maharashtra, Karnataka and Tamil Nadu out of 36 states and Union territories. In addition, many of the eight states that were included in the data had underreported numbers, making the de-facto tally of the number of deaths even higher. As the *Indian Express* report points out, several times the deaths of sewer workers are not confirmed by the state and as a consequence are not recorded by the NCSK.

The NCSK, which is a statutory body set up by an Act of parliament, has been collating the number of deaths caused by manual scavenging estimates around 817 deaths since 1993 when the practice was outlawed in the country. In March 2017, the Supreme Court directed the government to identify the people who died cleaning sewers from 1993 onwards and offer Rs 10 lakh as compensation to each of their families.

In the annual report that the NCSK submitted to the parliament, the commission noted the Swachh Bharat Abhiyan "should not focus just on toilet building but also on eradication of manual scavenging or workers' rehabilitation". The report also identified the Indian Railways as the "largest employer of *safai karamcharis*" (The Wire, 2019)

Conclusion

In this paper we strived to understand the available literature to study manual scavengers with accordance to Law. In order to do this, we reviewed literature from government reports, commission's recommendations, policies reports, Independent studies, Press Releases and other relevant literature. We observed certain themes across various available literature that its combination of law framework and accurate decision making to address such issues. Prohibition or such practices and prevalence of activities still remain there due to inactive response from judiciary system. The basic assumptions regarding indulging in practices is based on lack of equal opportunities provided to people and constant discrimination at every level and suppress the rights of people of such communities and force them to continue their profession.

We have presented a brief yet accurate literature for understanding legal framework and policy outcomes and differences in every literature regarding same issues. We find that most of the legal provision has to be strictly followed by people and justice to those who suffer from injustice. With available literature we were able to find some impact on global platforms in lights of Human Rights. There are some exceptions focusing on Caste based discrimination and other atrocities matters as well.

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